

ULTRASONIC MEASUREMENT OF ANISOTROPIC ELASTIC CONSTANTS OF ALUMINA/ALUMINUM COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Transversely isotropic elastic constants of alumina/aluminum composite, 99.9% pure aluminum reinforced with almost unidirectionally aligned short alumina fibers of $3\mu\text{m}$ in diameter and $200\mu\text{m}$ in length, are evaluated based on ultrasonic velocity measurements. The velocities of the longitudinal and transverse waves oscillating along the fiber direction are found to be significantly higher than those in other directions. The longitudinal Young modulus E_L is proportional to the fiber volume fraction. The prediction by the law of mixture is higher than the measured, while Hukuda and Kawata's prediction is close to the our results.

Keywords: Metal matrix composites, elastic constants, ultrasonic velocity, short fiber, anisotropy.

1. INTRODUCTION

Metal matrix composites reinforced with short fibers have such merit as relatively high stiffness and strength at elevated temperature, and availability of similar manufacturing process to the common metals. Therefore their application to aviation as well as civilian goods are expected in the future. Usual MMC reinforced by short fibers has no specific fiber orientation, however, higher stiffness and strength in a certain orientation is required for some particular application. Thus a MMC have developed, which is solidified under high pressure after making molten aluminum to permeate alumina preforms where the short fibers are aligned almost unidirectionally with an electrostatic method(1).

The measurement of the stiffness, elastic constants, of anisotropic composites is quite difficult to perform by the conventional tensile tests. Therefore several methods with ultrasonic velocity measurement have been reported for quasi-isotropic metal matrix composites(2-5). For MMC reinforced with almost unidirectional short fibers, however, the validity of ultrasonic velocity measurement for determination of anisotropic elastic moduli has not ben discussed yet. In this paper, the transversely isotropic elastic constants of an aluminum composite reinforced with almost unidirectionally aligned short aluminum fibers are determined based on the measurement of ultrasonic longitudinal and transverse wave velocities. The values thus obtained are compared with theoretical predictions by the law of mixture, Cox(6) and Fukuda and Kawata(7).

2. THE RELATION BETWEEN WAVE VELOCITIES AND ANISOTROPIC ELASTIC STIFFNESS

The elastic stiffness tensor of the orthotropic solid, referred with the principal axes of the orthotropy, is given by

$$C = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{13} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{12} & C_{22} & C_{23} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{13} & C_{23} & C_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{55} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{66} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Figure 1. Coordinate system.

Transverse isotropy can be assumed for the composite in which fibers are parallel to the axis 3 and the distribution of the fibers is uniform in the plane 1-2 (Figure 1), where $C_{11}=C_{22}$, $C_{13}=C_{23}$, $C_{44}=C_{55}$ and $C_{66}=(C_{11}-C_{12})/2$. Thus the number of independent constants is reduced to five. The wave velocities propagating through the transversely isotropic solid are given by the well known Christoffel equations.

$$(C_{ijkl}n_jn_l - \rho v^2 \delta_{ik})P_i = 0 \quad (2)$$

where, C , \mathbf{n} , ρ and \mathbf{P} denote the elastic stiffness tensor, unit normal vector to the wave front, density of the solid and wave amplitude vector. From these equation, the longitudinal and transverse wave velocities propagating along the principal axes are given by

$$\begin{aligned} V_L^1 &= \sqrt{C_{11}/\rho}, V_L^2 = \sqrt{C_{22}/\rho}, V_L^3 = \sqrt{C_{33}/\rho} \\ V_T^{12} &= V_T^{21} = \sqrt{C_{66}/\rho}, V_T^{31} = V_T^{32} = \sqrt{C_{44}/\rho} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where, the first and second suffixes of V_T denote the directions of \mathbf{n} and \mathbf{P} . The remaining constant C_{23} is determined by measuring the wave velocity(8) propagating in the direction bisecting the axes 2 and 3, which is written as

$$\rho V^2 = \frac{1}{4} \left\{ C_{22} + C_{33} \pm \sqrt{(C_{22} - C_{33})^2 + 4(C_{23} + C_{44})^2} \right\} + \frac{1}{2} C_{44} \quad (4)$$

The conventional elastic constants are given by inversion of the matrix C

$$S = \begin{bmatrix} 1/E_1 & -v_{21}/E_2 & -v_{31}/E_3 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -v_{12}/E_2 & 1/E_2 & -v_{32}/E_3 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -v_{13}/E_3 & -v_{23}/E_3 & 1/E_3 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/G_{23} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/G_{31} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/G_{12} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

3. MATERIAL AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

3.1 Alumina/aluminum composite

The composite tested is composed of 99.9% pure aluminum(1N90) and the short alumina fibers of which properties are shown in Table 1. The fiber volume fraction varied from 16% to 22%. Circular plate-like preforms of almost unidirectionally aligned alumina fibers were produced with an electrostatic method(1). The composites in 10 mm thick were casted with aluminum and solidified under high pressure, and machined into circular plates of 8mm thick and 60 mm in diameter. The cube specimens of 8mm in length were cut from the circular plates. Figure 2 shows microstructure of the composite. It should be noted that the fibers are not perfectly straight nor perfectly aligned unidirectionally, different from the long fibers with high stiffness. The distribution of fibers in the plane normal to the fiber axis is nearly uniform.

Table 1. Properties of alumina fiber.

Composites	Al ₂ O ₃ :95%, SiO ₂ :5%
Average Diameter	3 μm
Average Length	200 μm
Density	3300kg/m ³
Young's Modulus	300GPa
Tensile Strength	2GPa

(parallel to fibers)

(perpendicular to fibers)

Figure 2. Micrograph of alumina/aluminum composite.

3.2 Measurement of wave velocity

The schematic diagram of a digital measurement system of ultrasonic velocities is shown in Figure 3. Normal incidence transducers were used for the longitudinal(10MHz, 1/4") and transverse waves(5MHz, 1/4"). A series of the first and second back-wall echoes were added 256 times into the memory of a personal computer thorough an A/D board at a maximum sampling rate 800MHz. The digital zero-crossing method(9) was applied to determine the time-of-flight between two echoes.

Figure 3. Schematic diagram of measurement system.

4. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Ultrasonic velocity

Table 2 shows the measured wave velocities of the composite and aluminum matrix. The error of the velocities is estimated to be $\pm 5\text{m/s}$. Figure 4 shows the change in the longitudinal and transverse velocities oscillating along the fiber direction with the fiber volume fraction, from which linear correlation is observed. Table 2 shows that the longitudinal and transverse velocities oscillating along the fiber direction are apparently higher than those in other directions. This means that the reinforcement by the short fibers works according to expectation. In addition, the fiber direction can be easily detected with this fact. Another method to detect the fiber orientation is shown in Figure 5. When the polarization direction of the transverse wave is different from the fiber direction, the echo waves appear slightly distorted due to the birefringence. Thus the difference between the time delays at the first and second zero-crossing points varies with the angle of rotation.

Table 2. Wave velocities in various direction (m/s).

Plane	1	2	3	45°	1N90
$V_f=22\% \quad \rho=2860\text{kg/m}^3$					
Longitudinal: v_L	6878	6875	7241	7069	6260
Transverse: v_T	*2 3488 *3 3578	*1 3483 *3 3548	*1 3571 *2 3535	*2-3 3696	3150
$V_f=20\% \quad \rho=2840\text{kg/m}^3$					
Longitudinal: v_L	6855	6793	7222	7001	
Transverse: v_T	*2 3485 *3 3565	*1 3470 *3 3534	*1 3539 *2 3530	*2-3 3698	
$V_f=16\% \quad \rho=2800\text{kg/m}^3$					
Longitudinal: v_L	6736	6729	7026	6911	
Transverse: v_T	*2 3391 *3 3465	*1 3384 *3 3435	*1 3465 *2 3443	*2-3 3556	

*)Direction of polarization

Figure 4. Change in velocity with fiber volume fraction.

Figure 5. Change in echo waveform with angle between fiber direction and polarization of transverse wave.

4.2 Anisotropic elastic constants

The values of the engineering elastic constants evaluated from Equations (1) to (5) are listed in Table 3 with theoretical values for E_3 and E_1 calculated by the law of mixture, Cox(6), and Fukuda and Kawata(7). The other constants could not be calculated because detailed elastic properties of the alumina fibers were not available. The change of Young's moduli and Poisson's ratio with the fiber volume fraction is shown in Figures 6 and 7 with the prediction by the law of mixture. For E_3 , Fukuda and Kawata's estimation is close to the measured values, while for $E_1=E_2$ our results are close to the prediction by the law of mixture.

Table 3. Anisotropic elastic constants (GPa).

V_f (%)		E_3	E_1	G_{12}	G_{13}	ν_{12}	ν_{13}
22	Measured	109	94.3	34.6	36.4	0.356	0.316
	Predicted						
	Law of mixture	123	87.7				
	Cox	122					
	Fukuda & Kawata	114					
20	Measured	110	93.5	34.4	35.6	0.362	0.308
	Predicted						
	Law of mixture	119	86.2				
	Cox	118					
	Fukuda & Kawata	111					
16	Measured	100	87.7	33.2	33.4	0.365	0.315
	Predicted						
	Law of mixture	110	83.1				
	Cox	109					
	Fukuda & Kawata	104					

Figure 6. Longitudinal Young's modulus vs fiber volume fraction.

Figure 7. Poisson's ratio vs volume fraction.

5. CONCLUSION

The transversely isotropic elastic constants of aluminum matrix composite reinforced with short alumina fibers were determined based on velocity measurement of ultrasonic longitudinal and transverse waves. It is confirmed that both velocities increase linearly with the volume fraction of the fibers. In addition, the fiber orientation can be detected based on the following facts: waves oscillating along the fiber direction are faster than others; the change in the transverse waveforms of successive echoes with the angle between the polarization of the transverse wave and the fiber direction. The measured Young's modulus in the fiber direction is close to the prediction by Fukuda and Kawata, while the law of mixture gives higher estimation than the measured.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to express their gratitude to Mr.T.Ito at Toyoda Automatic Loom Works for preparing composite and to Mr.H.Yoshikawa at Nagoya Institute of Technology for help with the experiments.

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